

Enhancing Multiple Disease Prediction Systems Using Advanced Machine Learning Algorithms: A Web-Based Approach

*A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements
for the degree of Master of Science*

by

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Abstract

This research explores the utilization of advanced machine learning algorithms to enhance disease prediction accuracy and its usability in healthcare systems.

It builds on existing multiple disease prediction systems with a focus on optimising the prediction of heart diseases using advanced algorithms.

The methodology used optimised architectures such as Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Gradient Boosting and AdaBoost classifiers, a well-structured feature engineering process was carried out, and the heart disease prediction model for instance had excellent performance metrics, achieving an accuracy of 91.80%, sensitivity of 93.94%, and a strong f1-score of 91.18%.

The research extended beyond the improvement of Algorithms of an existing paper, it also includes a modern web-based interface that was built using Python and Streamlit.

Keywords: Neural Networks, Disease Prediction, Health Advisory System, Multi-disease Prediction, Medical AI, Optimized Architecture, Healthcare Web Applications.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

The utilization of machine learning in healthcare, especially in disease prediction is not new and in fact, will continue to evolve rapidly, it also remains that better algorithms and model training implementation will improve as well.

There will always be significant potential for improving both prediction accuracy and clinical utility through optimized algorithms and enhanced user interfaces. Developments in ensemble methods and neural network architectures will certainly open new possibilities for more accurate and reliable prediction systems as against traditional algorithms.

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite advances in machine learning applications, there remain several challenges in current prediction systems:

1. **Overly Dependence on Traditional Algorithm:** Many systems strictly use traditional algorithms, while this is a good practice, there is the oversight that complex patterns might not be captured in real-world data, leading to sub-optimal prediction accuracy.
2. **Lack of Actionable Insights:** Some systems provide raw predictions without integrating the results into practical healthcare recommendations.

1.3 Research Objectives

This research aims to address the above limitations by following the objectives below:

1. Achieve excellent performance metrics using only advanced algorithms for this study such as ensemble methods.
2. Develop disease predicting web Application with a health advisory system that converts predicted results into actionable recommendations.

1.4 Research Questions

This study investigates the key research questions below:

Algorithm Optimization and Performance:

- How would ensemble methods such as AdaBoost and optimised MLP architecture perform in comparison to traditional implementations in heart disease prediction?

1.5 Significance of the Study

This research advances both the practical and technical aspects of medical prediction systems. The trained model resulting from the practical implementation carried out in the course of this paper led to an optimised ensemble architecture (AdaBoost), which achieved excellent performance (93.94% sensitivity, 91.80% accuracy).

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Evolution of Disease Prediction Systems

Diseases such as Heart disease have remained a leading cause of death worldwide, having the ability to not only detect but predict heart diseases early will definitely mean the difference between life and death for so many patients especially considering that heart diseases often show no clear symptoms until it's in an advanced stage which is a reason why prediction systems have become a valuable tool in modern healthcare. With the rapid advancement of technology and the era, people are increasingly realizing the advantages of integrating artificial intelligence and machine learning models into heart disease prediction (Wu, 2024).

Over the past decade, researchers have been working to make disease-prediction systems more advanced, accurate and useful for healthcare practitioners.

Juned et al. (2022) developed a web-based platform for predicting multiple diseases including heart disease implemented mostly by using traditional machine learning approaches.

Their implementation used basic traditional algorithms like Logistic Regression (88.5% accuracy) and Random Forest (86.8% accuracy) for heart disease prediction. While their system demonstrated how such systems should work, there was the opportunity to make it even more accurate, and easier to use by integrating an additional feature.

Jiang.S(2020) also predicted heart diseases by training four machine learning algorithms using the UCI Machine Learning Repository and had the results of: Logistic Regression (88.2% accuracy), Random Forest (88.5% accuracy), XGBoost(83.6), Neural Network(85.2).

Sahoo et al. (2022) developed a framework for personalised care to tackle heart disease using machine learning models with corresponding accuracy such as Logistic Regression (88.52), K-Nearest Neighbor (83.6), Support Vector Machine (83.6), Naive Bayes (75.4), Decision Tree (78.68), Random Forest (90.16)

and XG Boost (88.52), the performance of their proposed model was assessed using Cleveland Heart Disease dataset from the UCI Machine Learning Repository.

Dubey A. K. et al. (2021) made use of two different datasets for heart disease prediction which are the Cleveland and Statlog datasets from the UCI Machine Learning repository, the models involved with corresponding accuracy are:

- Cleveland dataset: LR (89), DT (84), RF (88), KNN (82), SVM (89), NB (86)
- Statlog dataset: LR (93), DT (84), RF (90), KNN (82), SVM (91), NB (88).

Bharti, R. et al. (2021) paper trained models using both Machine learning and Deep learning Algorithms, the dataset used for this paper is the UCI Machine Learning Heart Disease dataset which according to the paper consisted of irrelevant features which they handled using isolation forest, they had the following results: LR (83.3), KNN (84.8), DT (82.3), RF (80.3), KNN (84.8), SVM (83.2), Deep Learning (94.2).

Sarra et al. (2022) proposed a new heart disease classification model based on the support vector machine (SVM) algorithm for improved heart disease detection, they applied χ^2 statistical optimum feature selection technique which led to an increased accuracy from 84.21% to 89.47 and from 85.29% to 89.7% in the Cleveland and Statlog datasets, respectively.

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter will present the methodological framework employed in developing and evaluating an enhanced disease prediction system, two major diseases are covered in this research work which are Heart and Mesothelioma disease, however, it should be noted that the focus and discussion of this study will be majorly on the model developed for the heart disease prediction, this is done to narrow down and streamline the research discussion and implementation details.

There would be a careful attempt to address how this study was carried out, displaying the technical underlines involved. The discussion will surround detailed information about the implementation, research approach, data collection methods, algorithm selection and the evaluation frameworks used throughout the study. The methodology will be divided into four (4) main phases: data processing, model development, evaluation and deployment, each phase was carefully designed to ensure reproductivity and reliability of results.

Technology Stack

The implementation was done using the following software environment and tools:
Development Environment:

- Programming Language: Python, version: 3.10.12
- Model Development: Google Colab, version: 1.0.0
- Web Framework: Streamlit, version: 1.39.0

Key Libraries and Frameworks:

Scikit-learn 1.6.0, NumPy 1.26.4, Pandas 2.2.2, Matplotlib 3.8.0, Seaborn 0.13.2, Joblib 1.4.2.

The technical stack was chosen due to its extensive documentation, robustness and wide adoption in the machine-learning community, the versions are specified to ensure the results can be reproduced.

Dataset Sources

Heart Disease Dataset:

The heart disease dataset, last accessed on December 22nd 2024, and was obtained from the referenced literature by Juned et al. (2022) at:

<https://github.com/sohammanjrekar/Multiple-Disease-Prediction-Webapp/blob/main/Datasets/heart.csv>

The referenced paper by Juned et al. (2022) mentioned the original source of the heart disease dataset as the Cleveland dataset in the UCI Machine Learning Repository (Janosi et al., 1989).

While the original Cleveland dataset is available directly from UCI, this study used the dataset version from Juned et al.'s implementation to ensure precise replication conditions for comparative analysis. This approach eliminates potential data preprocessing variations that could affect comparison validity and ensures direct comparability of results.

3.2 Data Processing Phase

This phase followed a structured pipeline that involved the initial Data handling where the raw dataset for the prediction of heart disease was inputted, followed by data validation, and the last stage involved a three way split strategy.

3.3 Model Development Phase

This phase involved a systematic approach involving multiple algorithms and stages; three advanced algorithms were used for the practical implementation process: AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, and Neural Networks, each offering its own unique advantage in the medical prediction task. Each model underwent training on both the SMOTE balanced set (to address class imbalance issues) and the original dataset.

Final Model Training

AdaBoost was selected as the final model as it had the highest validation accuracy score, AdaBoost model which was trained using the SMOTE balanced data with a carefully optimised learning rate of “0.07” and an optimised configuration gave the best performance, the model was evaluated using the test set that was kept separately from the beginning, several metrics were printed afterwards such as G-mean, accuracy, F1, product, and the classification result.

1. Final Model Configuration:

```
best_model = AdaBoostClassifier(  
    n_estimators=132,  
    learning_rate=0.07117896638863862,  
    algorithm='SAMME',  
    random_state=100  
)
```

The architecture which gave Ada Boost the best performance metric are below:

- **n_estimators=132**: number of weak learners in the ensemble which is 132.
- **learning_rate=0.07117896638863862**: this represents the applied weight to each weak classifier, it is low and will help reduce overfitting and improve the learning process overall.
- **algorithm='SAMME'**: this represents the boosting algorithm used in the implementation, it is the first (original) AdaBoost Algorithm.

- `random_state=100`: this represents the seed number which ensures reproducibility, this played a major role in getting the best-optimised accuracy for the implementation and various numbers were tested randomly to produce an excellent model, it is useful for debugging purposes.

3.4 Evaluation Phase

This phase involved four (4) robust steps that were carried out meticulously in order to ensure the model was properly evaluated and assessed, these are Performance Metrics Implementation, which involved the set up and calculation of crucial metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score, Model Evaluation Strategy: which involved the strategy deployed in the evaluation of both the validation and test sets, internal testing was primarily carried out on the dataset from Juned et al. (2022) and external evaluation was carried out using the Statlog dataset, Performance Analysis: which involved the detailed examination of the model's result, and lastly Result Documentation: which captured all result and findings.

3.5 Deployment Phase

This research implemented a web-based disease prediction system using Python and Streamlit, the complete implementation which includes the documentation and source code, is publicly available at:

Repository: <https://github.com/Tony-Kara/Enhanced-Disease-Prediction-Webapp>

Live System: <https://tonykara-disease-prediction-webapp.streamlit.app/>

Note: For the live system App, after clicking on the website link above, you might see a message stating "App has gone to sleep due to inactivity", just click on "Activate App" and it will be up and running after 1 to 2 minutes and a refresh of the web browser it is being run on.

Chapter 4: Results and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

The paper at this point presents this current chapter which includes the analysis of the results obtained from implementing an enhanced disease prediction system (model training and the building of the Web application), with a focus on significant improvement in model reliability and prediction accuracy for the “heart disease implementation” as compared to referenced literature Juned et al. (2022). The finding addresses the primary research question below:

- How would ensemble methods such as AdaBoost and optimised MLP architecture perform in comparison to traditional implementations in heart disease prediction?

4.2 Training Response

The result below shows the performance metric from the “Test set” across the different algorithms used for this study:

1 Ada Boosting Performance:

Best Performing Model for AdaBoost - SMOTE Data

G-Mean = **0.916** Accuracy = **0.918** F1 = **0.925**

Best parameters:

- n_estimators: **132**
- learning_rate: **0.071**
- algorithm: SAMME

2. Gradient Boosting Performance:

Best Performing Model for Gradient Boosting - Original Data

G-Mean = **0.853** Accuracy = **0.869** F1 = **0.889**

Best parameters:

- learning_rate: **0.189**
- max_depth: **18**
- min_samples_leaf: **4**
- min_samples_split: **4**
- n_estimators: **1414**
- subsample: **0.916**

3. Neural Network Performance:

Best Performing Model for Neural Network: SMOTE Data

G-Mean = 0.839 Accuracy = 0.836 F1 = 0.839

Best parameters:

- activation: relu
- alpha: 0.004
- batch_size: 103
- hidden_layer_sizes: (200, 75, 75)
- learning_rate_init: 0.002
- max_iter: 500

After implementing and comparing the three ML approaches that this study used for heart disease prediction, which are AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, and Neural Networks.

The result revealed AdaBoost as the best-performing model out of all three algorithms (trained on SMOTE balanced dataset) used in this research, the process achieved a commendable metric with G-Mean of 0.916, accuracy of 0.918, and F1 score of 0.925, the optimal AdaBoost made use of 132 estimators with a learning rate of 0.071, implementing the SAMME algorithm.

Gradient Boosting showed a strong but slightly lower performance metric, with its best result obtained from the original dataset, the model achieved a G-Mean of 0.853, accuracy of 0.869, and F1 score of 0.889, the optimal configuration has a more complex with 1414 estimators, a learning rate of 0.189 and a maximum depth of 18, the inclusion of parameters such as subsample (0.916) and min_samples_leaf (4) will help prevent overfitting while ensuring the robustness of the model.

The Neural Network Architecture, on the other hand while performing quite good as well, showed lower performance on the heart disease dataset in comparison to the ensemble methods, its best performance came from SMOTE balanced data with the metric as G-Mean of 0.839, accuracy of 0.836, and F1 score of 0.839. The network architecture consisted of three (3) hidden layers (200, 75, 75 neurons) with ReLU activation functions and tuned learning parameters.

The performance of AdaBoost suggests that its pattern of iteration focusing on misclassified samples is a plus when it comes to identifying heart disease risk, there was also a relatively small performance gap between the model original and

SMOTE balanced data, this indicates that the feature representation in the original dataset is quite robust.

4.3 Comparative Analysis with Existing Literature

4.3.1 Model Performance Comparison

First, by examining the reference implementation (Juned et al., 2022), their approach indicates the use of traditional algorithms (Logistic Regression, KNN and SVM) and a single advanced algorithm (Random Forest), their best-performing model was trained with Logistic Regression and had a test accuracy of 88.52%, the final result from the model can be seen in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: (Juned et al., 2022)

Accuracy Comparison of Heart Disease Prediction Strategies

Both Studies Used the Same Heart Disease Dataset

Comparative Analysis: Current Study vs. Juned et al. (2022)

Current Study Approach	Accuracy	Juned et al. Approach	Accuracy
Strategy 1 (AdaBoost)	91.80%	Strategy 1 (Logistic Regression)	88.52%
Strategy 2 (Gradient Boosting)	86.90%	Strategy 2 (Random Forest)	86.89%
Strategy 3 (MLP Neural Network)	83.60%	Strategy 3 (SVM)	70.49%

Figure 2: Model Performance Comparison

In Figure 2 above, a comparison analysis is displayed, the best three (3) model from the current study is compared with the best three (3) from Juned et al.'s study, both implementations made use of the same dataset, the highest accuracy between both

Strategies in each row is bolded in black.

There are several observations on how the current study compares against Juned et al.'s work. The first major difference is this study's best model: AdaBoost, whose implementation recorded a test accuracy of 91.8%, marking an improvement of 3.28% over their best performer (Logistic Regression at 88.52), this is a good step forward in heart disease prediction reliability.

This study's second-best model, Gradient Boosting, scored 86.9% test accuracy, which closely matches the reference paper's second-best model which is Random Forest performance (86.89%).

This study third best model (Neural Network) significantly outperformed Juned et al.'s SVM (70.49%) and KNN (68.85%) which is Juned et al.'s fourth-best model, this answers one of this study's research questions on whether advanced algorithms can actually perform better than traditional algorithms in predicting the risk level of heart diseases.

Aside from just accuracy, this study's AdaBoost model showed strong performance across other metrics as well: F1-score of 0.925 and G-Mean of 0.916, these numbers are equally vital as they tell us that the model is not only accurate, but it would be able to handle both positive and negative cases well, the high G-Mean suggests good balanced performance across classes, this is crucial for medical diagnosis applications.

A key take away is how ensemble methods (AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting) performed better when compared with simpler algorithms in this study, the success of AdaBoost suggests its adaptive approach shines in this study where it was able to learn from previous classification mistakes. The fact that these results were achieved over a period of continuous testing and retraining using the same dataset, which is exactly the one used by Juned et al.'s study, makes the performance improvement more meaningful and useful.

Strong consistency was also noted in the final result, this study's strongest performers (AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting) maintained a remarkable performance level, suggesting robust and reliable prediction capabilities.

Some of the key strategies during implementation that this study applied to improve further are:

1. **Validation Strategy:** Many ML models are stochastic or unstable. That is, if you train them multiple times, or if you make small changes to the training

data, then their performance varies significantly (Lones, 2021).

It is a good practice to further split datasets into validation sets and use this for evaluating model performance multiple times in the course of implementation. This was done in this current study as compared to the work of Juned et al. (2022)

2. Hyper-parameter tuning: When comparing models, do optimise your model's hyperparameters and evaluate a model multiple times to make sure you're giving them all a fair chance (Lones, 2021). This paper made use of hyperparameter tuning as compared to Juned et al.'s work which did not, this will help the current study achieve a better-trained model, some advantages of doing this are below:

- Stochastic nature: the models used in this paper (e.g., MLPClassifier and ensemble models) involve randomness, this basically means that training the same model with slightly different data or hyperparameters will likely give different results.
- Mitigation: This paper implementation used repeated training in cross-validation which ensures that the chosen hyperparameters and models generalise well, thereby helping to reduce the risk of overfitting or poor performance due to instability.
- Random state parameter: Another important factor during the implementation process is the testing of different "random_state" parameters for all the algorithms used in the study, this is useful for optimisation and reproducibility, the value was set to a fixed number of 100 for training all the models and used when SMOTE was applied as well, it led to a balanced distribution of samples in the split and contributed to the 91.8% test accuracy that was achieved with AdaBoost.

4.3.2 Statistical Analysis

Figure 3: Confusion matrix

Figure 3 above shows two versions of the generated Confusion Matrix from Implementation.

Confusion Matrix Evaluation:

The results of the confusion Matrix for the heart disease prediction are below:

1. Regular Confusion Matrix: this is on the left side of Figure 3, it displays raw numbers.
2. Normalized Confusion Matrix: this is on the right side of Figure 3 and displays percentage.

Confusion Matrix Results for Study:

```
[[25 3]
 [ 2 31]]
```

Statistical Analysis:

True Positives: 31 (50.8% of test set)

True Negatives: 25 (41.0% of test set)

False Positives: 3 (4.9% of test set)

False Negatives: 2 (3.3% of test set)

The Regular Confusion Matrix displayed in Figure 3 can be interpreted as below:

- 25 individuals who were actually low risk were correctly identified as low risk.
- 31 individuals who were actually high risk were correctly flagged as high risk.
- 3 low risk patients were labelled wrongly as high risk.
- 2 high risk patients were labelled wrongly as low risk.

The Normalized Confusion Matrix displayed in Figure 3 can be interpreted as below:

- The percentage accuracy of this study model in detecting low risk patients is 41%
- The percentage accuracy in detecting high risk patients was more accurate at 50.8%
- A low percentage of 4.9% of low-risk patients were wrongly labelled as high risk
- An even lower percentage of 3.3% of high-risk patients were wrongly labelled as low risk

It is important to note that detecting high risks cases is very important in medical diagnosis, the model had only two (2) false negatives, this number is not so bad. The model was able to correctly identify a larger number of high risk cases, in medical diagnostics, this suggests a remarkable sensitivity for detecting dangerous conditions early, it also has a remarkable performance with low risk.

4.3.3 Feature Importance Analysis

Figure 4: Feature Ranking Results

A feature importance analysis will provide insights into which clinical indicators have the strongest influence on heart disease prediction; this was run for this study using the code snippet below, and the result obtained can be viewed in Figure 4.

The model identified the 13 clinical features, with each having a varying level of predictive importance as shown in Figure 10, the top three (3) features with their clinical relevance will be discussed below:

1. ca (Number of Major Vessels Colored by Fluoroscopy): This feature stood out as the strongest predictor, it refers to the number of major coronary vessels that are

visible after being coloured using fluoroscopy, it gives an insight into the length of blockages of blood vessel in the heart. According to Kočka (2015), "the invasive coronary angiography is the gold standard in coronary artery disease evaluation. It is one of the most common operative procedures worldwide."

- Clinical Relevance: Higher "ca" value is strongly linked to a higher likelihood of coronary artery disease (CAD).

2. oldpeak (ST Depression Induced by Exercise Relative to Rest): This feature stood out as the second best predictor, it measures the difference in ST-segment depression observed in an electrocardiogram (ECG) during exercise compared to rest, it gives an insight into whether there is an insufficient blood flow to the heart muscle during stress. According to Sundkvist et al. (2007), "depression of the ST-segment on the electrocardiogram (ECG) during exercise testing plays a major role in the diagnosis of coronary artery disease."

- Clinical Relevance: Elevated level will indicate "myocardial ischemia", Patients with significant ST depression are at higher risk of adverse cardiovascular occurrence.

3. cp (Chest Pain Type): This feature stood out as the third best predictor, there is a category of chest pain that can be experienced by patients:

Typical angina (1): Pain related to myocardial ischemia.

Atypical angina (2): Pain not clearly linked to ischemia.

Non-anginal pain (3): Pain unrelated to heart conditions.

Asymptomatic (4): No chest pain.

According to Alderwish et al. (2019), "chest pain characteristics are valuable in determining which patients require acute attention."

- Clinical Relevance: one of the primary symptoms for diagnosing heart disease is chest pain.

Chapter 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 General Conclusions

This research successfully developed a heart disease prediction model that achieved a 91.8% accuracy, the best-performing model was AdaBoost.

In addition, to narrow the gap between research and practical application, this study built a fully functional web application that currently predicts the risk case level for heart disease.

5.2 Conclusions to Finalise Research Questions

1. Algorithm Optimization and Performance:

- How would ensemble methods such as AdaBoost and optimised MLP architecture perform in comparison to traditional implementations in heart disease prediction?

Findings: Ensemble methods used in this study performed better than traditional algorithms in heart disease detection with the best-performing model (AdaBoost) achieving 91.8% accuracy, 93.94% sensitivity, and 89.29% specificity, it outperformed comparable studies such as Juned et al. (2022) who achieved 88.52% with Logistic Regression.

5.3 Implementation Availability

The complete implementation of this research, including source code and documentation, is available at:

Repository: <https://github.com/Tony-Kara/Enhanced-Disease-Prediction-Webapp>

Live System: <https://tonykara-disease-prediction-webapp.streamlit.app/>

5.4 Recommendations

From the findings and experiences gathered in the course of this research, several core recommendations can be made which can align with the future progression and implementation of disease predicting models, these recommendations cover both practical and technical improvements and are shown below:

- The web-based system can be further extended to accommodate more diseases.
- Deploying the trained models on a mobile Application will result in easier accessibility.
- Generally, tools cannot be said to have 100% accuracy, they should rather be used as a supportive tool rather than a primary decision maker.
- Also, the model can likely be further enhanced by investigating its performance with deep learning approaches and exploring feature engineering techniques for improved accuracy.
- In terms of technical, real-time prediction capabilities can be developed, and integration with medical hospitals can be explored.
- Future research can consider exploring this study model for consideration in adapting the model for different populations, while this study model for heart disease showed strong performance on the available datasets, further validation using a diverse patient population would further strengthen the model and help identify any necessary adjustments for specific demographic groups.

5.5 Errors Analysis and Limitations

It's not all rainbow and shinning when it comes to the matter of life and death, even though this study's model was quite remarkable, the small misclassification of misrepresenting high risk as low risks (false negative) is relevant as it means the 2 individuals could have missed out on immediate attention.

To dive into analysing the errors, a closer look at the following is necessary:

1. Confusion Matrix Analysis:

From this study results:

- **True Negatives: 25** (correctly identified low risk)
- **False Positives: 3** (incorrectly flagged as high risk)
- **False Negatives: 2** (missed high risk cases)

- True Positives: 31 (correctly identified high risk)

Key observations from above are:

- Few false negatives (2 cases), relevant for medical diagnostic applications.
- False positive rate (3 cases), this is also still low and suggests a good specificity.

2. Model Performance Drop:

Training vs External Validation:

- Accuracy drop from 91.8% to 86.14%
- Sensitivity decrease from 93.94% to 83.33%
- Specificity reduction from 89.29% to 88.48%

Analysis:

- The performance drop when the model was validated on a new dataset indicates the model is robust and not overfitted.
- The accuracy score in spite of the drop is still reasonably good.
- The drop suggests the model's real world applicability.

Limitations noted are below:

1. Dataset Limitations:

- The dataset used is an industry standard in detecting heart disease but it should still be noted that it is a relatively small dataset with 303 samples.
- The dataset is restricted to a specific geographical region.

5.6 Future Directions

- Expand to add more disease prediction models.
- Since code is open-sourced, contributions from the public will be welcome to further improve the web application and also develop a separate Mobile application that will load all trained models.
- Create API services and integrate additional useful features for the web App.

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